

Bridging the Gap: Assessing the Activities of Traditional Birth Attendants in Maternal Mortality Reduction in Ado Local Government Area of Benue State, Nigeria

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Abstract:

Maternal mortality remains a pressing global health challenge, with pregnancy-related deaths largely preventable through adequate care and intervention. Despite various healthcare efforts, Nigeria and sub-Saharan Africa continue to experience high maternal mortality rates, highlighting gaps in existing strategies. This study examines the role of Traditional Birth Attendants (TBAs) in maternal morbidity and mortality, addressing gaps in previous research that overlooked TBAs' activities. Using a systematic literature review and Structural Functionalism perspectives which anchored on the system theory, the study evaluates TBAs sensitization activities, their influence on maternal mortality, and contributing factors. Conducted in four council wards of Ado Local Government Area, Benue State, the research involved 341 respondents, utilizing focused group discussions and semi-structured interviews. Findings revealed that maternal mortality will persist unless TBAs' activities are effectively regulated and integrated into skilled maternal healthcare frameworks. The study recommends a multidimensional intervention strategy, including improved healthcare infrastructure, access to skilled birth attendants, enhanced TBAs' training that is technologically and AI-powered. Strengthening collaboration between TBAs and skilled birth attendants is crucial for effective referrals and overall maternal health improvement.

Keywords: A-I Powered, Maternal Mortality, Traditional Birth Attendants.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Maternal mortality remains a major global health concern, especially in Nigeria and sub-Saharan Africa, where pregnancy-related deaths persist despite various healthcare efforts. Many of these deaths are preventable with adequate care, yet existing maternal health strategies have not sufficiently addressed underlying gaps. Traditional Birth Attendants (TBAs) play a vital role in rural maternal healthcare by conducting deliveries and providing care for pregnant women, especially in areas where government health facilities are inaccessible.

Despite their contributions, maternal mortality remains a major challenge in Nigeria, highlighting the need for effective strategies to integrate TBAs into formal healthcare systems (Olaore et al., 2020; Okpani et al., 2022). Recognizing their importance, the Federal Government of Nigeria initiated training programs for TBAs between 1997 and 2000, aiming to enhance their service delivery and reduce maternal mortality rates. As part of the Village Health Team (VHT), TBAs were tasked with encouraging women to seek antenatal and family planning services while limiting their delivery roles to emergency situations. However, despite these efforts, TBAs continue to conduct deliveries, raising concerns about their impact on maternal health outcomes (Okonofua et al., 2022; Tukur et al., 2022).

This study assesses how TBAs' revised responsibilities influence maternal mortality in Ado Local Government Area of Benue State. By examining their activities, the research aims to determine whether their integration into formal healthcare has led to significant improvements or if further interventions are required to enhance maternal health and reduce pregnancy-related deaths in rural communities (NPC, 2019; Akinsola et al., 2025).

1.1 Scope and significance of the study

The research is geographically limited to Ado LGA, focusing on the effects of TBAs on maternal mortality. It underscores the ongoing challenge of maternal deaths despite governmental and non-governmental interventions. The study seeks to uncover hidden factors influencing maternal mortality rates and provide data to inform future policies aimed at improving maternal health outcomes. By highlighting TBAs' contributions, challenges, and integration into healthcare frameworks, the findings will be relevant to both governmental and non-governmental organizations working to enhance maternal healthcare.

1.2 Aim and objectives of the study

1.2.1 Aim

This study aims to critically examine the role of Traditional Birth Attendants (TBAs) in maternal health and mortality in Ado Local Government Area (LGA), Benue State. By assessing TBAs' activities, their influence on maternal health outcomes, and contribution to socio-cultural and structural factors, the study seeks to provide insights into how TBAs

can be effectively integrated into formal healthcare frameworks to improve maternal health and reduce mortality rates.

1.2.2 Specific objectives

1. To determine the number of Traditional Birth Attendants (TBAs) in Ado LGA and assess their distribution within the community.
2. To investigate the maternal mortality sensitization activities and services provided by TBAs in Ado LGA, evaluating their effectiveness in promoting maternal health awareness.
3. To analyze the effects of TBAs' activities and services on maternal mortality, identifying both positive contributions and potential risks.
4. To examine the factors facilitating or hindering maternal mortality reduction efforts, including socio-economic, healthcare infrastructure, and policy-related challenges.
5. To propose strategies for improving maternal healthcare services by strengthening TBAs' regulation, training, and engagement within local and national maternal health policies.

1.3 Hypothesis

The study operates under two assumptions: (1) No significant relationship exists between TBAs' sensitization activities and maternal mortality reduction, and (2) no significant correlation between the number of TBAs and their sensitization efforts.

2. OPERATIONAL LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Maternal health

Maternal health refers to the health of women during pregnancy, childbirth, and the postnatal period. Each stage should be a positive experience, ensuring women and their babies reach their full potential for health and well-being (Akinsola et al., 2025).

2.2 Maternal mortality

Maternal mortality is defined as the death of a woman while pregnant or within 42 days of termination of pregnancy, irrespective of the duration and site of the pregnancy, from any cause related to or aggravated by the pregnancy or its management, but not from accidental or incidental causes (Adedokun et al., 2023).

2.3 Reproductive health

Reproductive health is a state of complete physical, mental, and social well-being and not merely the absence of disease or infirmity, in all matters relating to the reproductive system and its functions and processes (Iwu et al., 2021; Akute, 2023).

2.4 Maternal mortality ratio (MMR)

The maternal mortality ratio (MMR) is the number of maternal deaths per 100,000 live births during a given time period (Iwu et al., 2021, Adedokun et al., 2023).

2.5 Maternal Mortality Rate

Maternal mortality rate refers to the number of maternal deaths in a given period per 100,000 women of reproductive age during the same time period (Okpani et al., 2022).

2.6 Traditional birth attendant (TBA)

Traditional Birth Attendant (TBA) is a lay midwife who provides basic health care, support, and advice during pregnancy and childbirth, based on experience and knowledge acquired informally through ancestral traditions and practices of the communities where they originated in Nigeria (Akute et al., 2023; Akinsola et al., 2025).

2.7 Skilled birth attendant (SBA)

SBA is a healthcare professional who has been trained to provide high-quality care during pregnancy, child-birth, and the postpartum period (Iwu et al., 2021; Adedokun et al., 2023).

2.8 Socio-cultural context in maternal health

The socio-cultural context refers to the surrounding societal and cultural factors that influence maternal health, including traditional beliefs, gender roles, religious practices, and economic conditions. TBAs, as key community healthcare providers, play a vital role in maternal care, particularly in under-served areas. Recognizing their influence, the study emphasizes structured regulation, training, and collaboration as essential components for improving maternal health outcomes (NPC, 2019; Olaore et al., 2020; Adedokun et al., 2023).

3. METHODOLOGY

This study integrates quantitative and qualitative research methods to provide a comprehensive understanding of traditional birth attendants (TBAs) in maternal health, focusing on their distribution, sensitization activities, and collaboration with formal healthcare systems.

3.1 Study design

A mixed-methods approach was employed to analyze TBAs' role in maternal healthcare. Quantitative methods determined the number and distribution of TBAs and assessed

statistical correlations, while qualitative methods explored maternal mortality sensitization activities, TBAs' effectiveness, and socio-cultural influences.

3.2 Study area

The study was conducted in Ado Local Government Area (LGA), Benue State, Nigeria, a rural region in the North Central zone. The area faces economic and social challenges due to ethnic conflicts between the Idoma and Igbo groups, which hinder employment and education. Farming is the primary occupation, with the Idoma people being the dominant ethnic group. Economic development is constrained by poor transportation networks and inadequate infrastructure, limiting access to essential social services. Many wards have only one Primary Health Centre (PHC), often lacking sufficient staff, sanitation, electricity, and water supply, which particularly affects pregnant women's access to maternal healthcare.

3.3 Study population

The study focused on women aged 15-49 years in Ado LGA as the reproductive age group. The total population of Ado LGA is 233,400, with eligible participants being women who had given birth in the past year or were currently pregnant. Women in this category constituted 22 % of the LGA's population (Bola et al 2024, NPC ,2019). The common denominator among participants was their reproductive status and residence in Ado LGA.

3.4 Sampling techniques

A purposive sampling technique was used to select a representative sample. Participants were drawn from households, general hospitals, Traditional Birth Attendants (TBAs) homes, and Primary Health Centres (PHCs) across council wards.

3.5 Sample size

Data collection involved 400 women, selected based on the Benue State Ministry of Health's records (Bola et al., 2024; Onuh et al., 2024), which estimated 51,348 women in the reproductive age range (15-49 years) in Ado LGA. The sample size was determined using the Yaro Yamane formula:
$$N = \frac{233400}{1 + 233400 (0.0025)}$$

$N = 400$. Initially, 400 women were planned for selection across council wards. However, logistic conditions including transportation costs, challenging terrain, and farm commitments reduced the final sample size to 341 respondents.

3.5 Method of data collection

Data collection methods included: The primary data were obtained through Survey, Focus Group Discussion (FGD) and semi-structured interviews (SSI). Which were conducted on the women, nurses, village heads, and medical professionals. FGDs were exclusively conducted with TBAs, because many were non-literate, making written surveys impractical. The questionnaire was structured into different sections to capture: Social, cultural, and economic factors influencing maternal health and women's responses to maternal mortality challenges.

Survey Instrument: This part has four sections to measure key study variables:

Section A: Socio-demographic characteristics of respondents.

Section B: Interview guide for medical practitioners.

Section C: Reproductive history of women aged 15-49, including reproductive health behavior and place of delivery.

Section D: FGDs with TBAs on delivery practices, complication management, knowledge acquisition, and instruments used. The responses provided critical insights into maternal health dynamics, ensuring representation across educated and non-literate women, both married and unmarried.

4. RESULTS

Table 1: Demographic characteristics of reproductive aged respondents

Variables	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Age in years		
15-19	42	12.3
20-24	54	15.8
25-29	185	54.3
30-34	55	16.1
35-39	5	1.5
Mean 31.9		
Total	341	100
Marital Status		
Single	43	12.6
Married	188	55.1
Divorced	15	4.4
Widowed	47	13.8
Cohabiting	48	14.1
Total	341	100
Religion		
Christianity	205	60.1
Islam	5	1.5
Traditional	105	30.8
Free Thinker	26	7.6
Total	341	100
Educational Qualification		
No formal	86	25.2
Primary	158	46.3
Secondary school	72	21.1
Tertiary	25	7.3
Total	341	100
Occupation		
Petty Trading	106	31.1
Farming	149	43.7
Civil servant	41	12.0
Unemployed	30	8.8
Other	15	4.4
Total	341	100

The study found a mean participant age of 31.9 years, with many women of childbearing in their late thirties. More than half of the respondents (54.3%) were within the 25–29 age bracket, while none fell within the 40–49 age range. In terms of marital status, the majority (55.1%) were married, 12.6% identified as single mothers, 14.1% were cohabiting, and 4.4% were divorced. Religious affiliation showed that most respondents were Christians (60.1%), followed by traditional worshippers (30.8%). Educational attainment varied considerably: 25.2% had no formal education, 46.3% had completed primary education, 21.1% had attained secondary education, and only 7.3% had reached tertiary

level. Occupational distribution revealed that farming was the predominant occupation (43.7%), followed by petty trading (31.1%). Civil servants accounted for 12.0%, while 8.8% were unemployed and 4.4% engaged in other forms of work.

Table 2: Number of TBAs and sources of training in study area

Category	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Number of TBA in Ado LGA		
Male	0	0
Female	39	100
Total	39	100
Age		
31-40	3	7.7
41-50	5	12.8
51-60	31	79.5
Total	39	100
Level of education		
No formal education	31	79.5
Primary education	6	15.4
Secondary education	2	5.1
Total	39	100
Marital status		
Married	29	74.4
Widowed	10	25.6
Total	39	100
Religion		
Traditional religion	30	76.9
Christianity	9	23.1
Total	39	100
Sources of Training		
No training	3	7.7
Apprenticeship with relatives	30	76.9
Church	4	10.2
Apprenticeship with non-relatives	2	5.1
Total	39	100
Number of TBA trained to use modern facilities (PPE)	12	30.8

The study found that all 39 Traditional Birth Attendants (TBAs) interviewed were elderly females, with 79.5 % lacking formal education and none registered with the Local Government. Most (76.9 %) acquired their skills through apprenticeship with relatives, while only 30.8 % had received formal training, mainly from NGOs on PPE use. There was no record of male TBAs in this study.

Table 3: Activities and services provided by TBAs in study area

Activities of TBAs	Frequency	Percentage
Delivery	39	100.0
Treatment of infertility and infection	25	64.1
Antenatal-care	30	76.9
Circumcision of babies	10	25.6
Management of threatened abortion	5	12.8
Treatment of convulsion in children	10	25.6
Abdominal massage for women with abdomen pain	5	12.8
Types of Medication given to patients by traditional birth Attendants		
Leaves	39	100.0
Roots	32	82.0
Scarification mark	15	38.5
Palm kernel pomade	30	76.9
Lizard	10	12.6

Traditional Birth Attendants (TBAs) in Ado LGA provide a wide range of reproductive health services, including antenatal care, childbirth, infertility treatment, threatened abortion management, and infant circumcision. While all TBAs assist with deliveries, only 64.1% address infertility issues, 12.8 % manage threatened abortions, and 25.6 % perform circumcisions.

TBAs rely on traditional medications such as leaves (100 %), roots (82 %), and scarification marks (38.5 %), with some using rituals in patient care, which is more prevalent among those without formal education. Notably, some TBAs use animals like lizards (12.6 %) and scarification marks (38.5 %) as treatments, posing risks of infections like hepatitis B and HIV when equipment is shared. Infection prevention remains inadequate, as 73.3 % do not recommend tetanus toxoid vaccinations, contrasting

findings in Thailand where TBAs universally neglect this practice. Overall, TBAs play a vital role in maternal care but require improved training, infection control measures, and integration with formal healthcare systems to enhance safety and effectiveness.

Table 4: Effects of activities of traditional birth attendants on maternal mortality on study site

Categories	Frequency	Percentage (%)
TBA are effective		
Yes	85	24.9
No	256	75.1
Total	341	100
TBAs Helpful to pregnant women		
Yes	314	92.1
No	27	7.9
Total	341	100
TBAs are Skilled		
Yes	75	21.9
No	266	78.1
Total	341	100

The study on traditional birth attendants (TBAs) in Ado LGA reveals a negative impact on maternal mortality, with 75.1 % of cases showing poor outcomes. This aligns with prior research, attributing issues to inadequate training and a lack of collaboration between TBAs and health workers. Despite their limitations, most women (92.1 %) still find TBAs useful, with 78.1 % believing they possess skills, largely because TBAs remain their only accessible option.

According to TBA in a focus group discussion: “This hospital people do not do their work better than us yet they treat us like dirt”. This confirms the tip from an informant that TBAs and health workers can be compared to cats and dogs that is, not in good terms with each other due to the assertion that TBAs complicate issues and leave the trouble of management for the skilled birth professional.

Table 5: Factors that hinder the reduction of maternal mortality in Ado LGA

Management of Delivery Complication by TBAs:	Frequency	Percentage
What TBAs do in case of obstructed labour		
Trained		
Refer to the hospital	12	30.8
Maternal effort	2	5.1
Bed rest	3	7.7
Untrained		
Manipulate womb manually	15	38.5
Use herbal preparation	5	12.8
Don' t know what to do	2	5.1
Total	39	100
Management of retained placenta		
Trained		
Refer to the hospital	12	30.8
Untrained		
Give herbal preparation	17	43.6
Press on abdomen	10	25.4
Total	39	100
Management of severe bleeding		
Trained		
Refer to the hospital		
Use ice pack if any	12	30.6
	0	0
Untrained		
Tilt bed head down		
Pack vagina with clean clothes	10	25.4
Wear charm	10	25.4
Giver herbal preparation	2	5.1
Total	5	12.8
	39	100

TBA uses facilities		
Yes	320	93.8
No	21	6.2
Total	341	100
TBA uses modern facilities like gloves, apron, scissors, methylated spirit, razor, germicides e.t.c		
Yes	120	35.2
No	221	64.8
Total	341	100
TBA are hygienic		
Yes	147	43.1
No	194	56.9
Total	341	100
TBA should be trained and assisted		
Yes	317	93.0
No	24	7.0
Total	341	100
TBA should continue to offer services		
Yes	341	100
No		
Do you intend to continue with TBA		
Yes	234	68.6
No	107	31.3
Total	341	100

Traditional Birth Attendants (TBAs) in Ado LGA face major challenges in managing delivery complications. Only 30.6 % refer severe cases like obstructed labor and hemorrhage to formal healthcare facilities, with education playing a crucial role, more educated TBAs are likelier to make referrals. Record-keeping is poor, with only educated TBAs maintaining records. Infection control measures are inadequate, as 64.8 % of TBAs lack any form of proper hygiene practices, and personal protective equipment is rarely used.

Despite these risks, women continue to patronize TBAs due to barriers in accessing formal healthcare, including hospital costs, distance, and staff attitudes. To reduce maternal mortality, TBAs require improved training and better facilities, ensuring they can provide safer and more effective maternal care. Healthcare professionals should collaborate with

TBAs, accepting referrals and working toward integrating them into a broader healthcare framework rather than dismissing them outright.

5. DISCUSSION

The findings highlight the complex role of traditional birth attendants (TBAs) in maternal healthcare within the study area. While TBAs remain a critical alternative for women who face barriers to accessing formal health facilities, their practices raise concerns about safety and effectiveness. Cultural ties and community trust continue to sustain their patronage, even when respondents express doubts about their competence. This tension underscores the dual reality of TBAs as both a vital resource and a potential risk in maternal care (Olaore et al., 2020).

Socioeconomic and infrastructural challenges strongly influence reliance on TBAs. High hospital fees, long travel distances, poor road networks, and shortages of trained medical personnel make formal healthcare inaccessible for many rural women. Negative experiences with healthcare staff, including perceived rudeness and inefficiencies, further discourage hospital visits. These systemic issues reinforce the dependence on TBAs, positioning them as the most available and culturally acceptable option for many families (Okpani et al., 2022).

The study also reveals important demographic patterns. Women with lower levels of education are more likely to rely on TBAs, suggesting that awareness and knowledge significantly shape healthcare choices. Despite their widespread involvement in assisting pregnant women, only a small proportion of TBAs have received formal training. This gap in skills limits their ability to identify high-risk pregnancies and make timely referrals, which is critical for reducing maternal and neonatal mortality (Adedokun et al., 2023; Bolariwa et al., 2024).

Another challenge lies in the strained relationship between TBAs and orthodox health professionals. Hostility and lack of collaboration hinder the integration of TBAs into mainstream healthcare systems. Yet, evidence suggests that when TBAs are trained and supported, they can complement formal health services and contribute to safer deliveries. The evolving landscape of maternal healthcare, particularly with the introduction of digital health innovations, presents opportunities to redefine the role of TBAs. By equipping them with modern tools and structured training, TBAs can transition into community-based facilitators who bridge the gap between tradition and modernity (Olaore et al., 2020; Okpani et al.,).

6. CONCLUSION

Traditional Birth Attendants (TBAs) remain central to maternal healthcare in rural communities due to systemic challenges such as limited access to formal health facilities. Their cultural role, experience, and community trust make them indispensable in childbirth services. However, the gap between TBAs and modern healthcare systems must be bridged to improve maternal and neonatal outcomes.

The evolving role of TBAs highlights the importance of integrating them into formal healthcare frameworks rather than dismissing their contributions. With the rise of digital health innovations and AI-driven tools, TBAs can transition into community-based facilitators of maternal health, working alongside skilled birth attendants to ensure safer deliveries. While universal access to skilled healthcare providers remains the ultimate goal, empowering TBAs with modern training and technology can significantly reduce maternal mortality and enhance maternal health outcomes in underserved areas.

6.1 Recommendations

Capacity building: Governments and NGOs should identify skilled TBAs and provide structured training programs on hygiene, safe delivery practices, and early detection of high-risk pregnancies.

Integration into healthcare systems: TBAs should be formally recognized and incorporated into maternal health frameworks through collaboration and mutual respect with healthcare professionals.

Technology-driven training: Mobile health (mHealth) platforms, AI-powered diagnostic tools, telemedicine referrals, and AR-based emergency simulations should be prioritized to enhance TBAs' effectiveness.

Health education role: TBAs should expand beyond delivery services to provide technology-assisted antenatal and postnatal education, including SMS reminders, wearable monitoring devices, and mobile counseling apps.

AI-enhanced interventions: Introduce AI-assisted nutrition planning, smart drug distribution systems, and blockchain-based maternal health records to improve maternal care quality and safety.

Collaboration with health centers: Strengthen partnerships between TBAs and health facilities using AI-driven analytics, automated resource allocation, and emergency alert systems for high-risk pregnancies.

Policy and funding support: Governments should promote AI-enabled maternal care solutions through public-private partnerships, incentives for technology adoption, and predictive models for healthcare investment.

Public health campaigns: Launch AI-powered awareness programs to encourage institutional deliveries, improve maternal health practices, and guide strategies for reducing maternal mortality.

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